

Demographic Study of Leiomyoma Cases in Tertiary Care Center in Rajasthan

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Aim and Objective: To analyze the demographics of women presenting with leiomyoma with respect to: Age, symptoms, location etc.

Settings and Design: This was an observational study carried out in a tertiary health center for a period of 1 year from September 2022 to September 2023.

Materials and Methods: A retrospective observational study was conducted in 35 women having pain in abdomen, abnormal uterine bleeding, who were presented to the department of obstetrics and gynaecology, National Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Jaipur between sept 2022 and sept 2023. All the patient presented with above mentioned symptoms were studied after obtaining consent from participant. Ultrasound was done and location of leiomyoma was studied. Fibroid were studied in terms of its, location and most common presenting symptoms and age of occurrence of symptoms.

Results: In our study, the most common age group of presentation was 36-40 years. Most common type of fibroid was intramural (62.8 %) Most common symptoms was menorrhagia (57.1%). Most commonly associated with nulligravida (49.5%).

Keywords: Ultrasound; Clinical Symptoms; Abnormal Uterine Bleeding.

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Introduction

Uterine fibroid is the most common benign monoclonal tumor of uterus originating from the smooth muscle of myometrium occurring most commonly during the middle and late reproductive age group. [1] It contains large aggregation of extracellular matrix composed of collagen, elastin, fibronectin and proteoglycan. [1] The estimated cumulative incidence of Leiomyoma by the age 50 was more than 80% for African women and nearly 70% for Caucasian women. [2] Presenting symptoms depends most commonly upon the size and location of the fibroid. Patient may present with pain in abdomen, abnormal uterine bleeding, dysmenorrhea [3,4,5] Sometime patients may present with urinary symptoms like urinary frequency or urgency⁵

FIGO Classification Categorizes leiomyoma as:

Submucosal, Intramural, Subserosal and transmural fibroids:

Type 0 Intracavitary

Type 1 Less than 50 % of fibroid diameter within the myometrium.

Type 2 50 % or more of the fibroid diameter within the myometrium.

Type 3 about the endometrium without any intracavitary component

Type 4 Intramural and entirely within the myometrium, without extension to either the endometrial surface or to the serosa

Type 5 Subserosal at least 50 % intramural.

Type 6 Subserosal less than 50 % intramural.

Type 7 Subserosal attached to the serosa by a stalk
Type 8 No involvement of the myometrium; includes cervical lesions, those in the round or broad ligament without direct attachment to the uterus and "parasitic" fibroids.

Materials and Methods

The Retrospective observational study was carried out in 35 women (reproductive and perimenopausal age group) visiting gynecological OPD in NIMS Hospital, Jaipur, with leiomyoma symptoms. The Data was collected from September 2022 to September 2023 for a period of 1 year. Informed Consent was obtained from each patient. All the patients with above mentioned symptoms underwent ultrasound and results were obtained.

Inclusion Criteria

Women of reproductive and perimenopausal age group with leiomyoma with symptoms like pain in abdomen, menorrhagia.

Exclusion Criteria: Unmarried women with leiomyoma. Women with other comorbidities such as bleeding disorders, heart disease, renal disease. Women on concurrent anticoagulation therapy.

Result

Among the selected sample population, the most

common age of presentation was 36-40 years (57.1%). The risk factors of leiomyoma includes sedentary life styles, diet rich in red meat and lack of green leafy vegetables. First degree relatives of patients with fibroids also have a risk of developing Fibroids as per studies.[6]

Table 1: Most common fibroid was intramural as shown in Table 1 (62.8%).

Fibroid Type	Total	Percentage
Intramural	22	62.8 %
Subserosal	9	25.71 %
Submucosal	4	11.42 %

Ultrasound is the most readily available and least costly imaging technique to differentiate fibroids from other pelvic pathology. [7]

Fibroids can be managed medically or surgically.

Surgical option include myomectomy, laparoscopic myomectomy, laparoscopic radio frequency ablation, hysteroscopic myomectomy, endometrial ablation and abdominal hysterectomy. [8,9,10]

Table 2: Most common presentation was menorrhagia (57.1%).

Symptoms	Total	Percentage
Memorrhagia	20	57.1%
Dysmenorrhoea	5	14.2%
Pain in abdomen	8	22.85%
Asymptomatic	2	5.71%

Table 3: Fertility and Fibroid

Types of Fibroids	Fertility
Submucosal	12%
Intramural	40%
Subserosal	80%

The above table shows that presence of submucosal fibroid decreases the fertility rate to a significant level. The presence of intramural fibroid does not affect the fertility rate significantly. Also, presence of subserosal fibroid has no effect of fertility rate. Out of 35 women, 12 patients were managed medically while 23 patients underwent surgery, either conservative (medical) or definitive. (Myomectomy or hysterectomy).

Discussion

Uterine fibroid is the most common benign tumor of the uterus accounting for approximately 60 % of the total cases. [1] It most commonly occurs at the reproductive age group as shown in our study, around 57.1% women were belonging to age group of 36-40 years. [1] As stated in study by Wallach and Bukulmez, symptoms of fibroid depends upon the type of fibroid, most common being menorrhagia as depicted in our study. Around 57.1% women had menorrhagia as their presenting complaint. [4] Other symptoms includes pain in abdomen, dysmenorrhea. About 5% of the fibroid remains asymptomatic and are always an incidental finding. [1]

Also the most common type of fibroid is intramural which is showed in our study (62.8%) which matches with the study done by Laughlin.[5] Most of the fibroid remains asymptomatic and hence do

not require any treatment. While symptomatic fibroid are managed either by medical method or surgical method. Submucosal fibroid is the most common fibroid leading to infertility as shown in our study, leading to only 12% of fertility rate as compared to sub serosal and intramural which adds to significant value for fertility rate (80% and 40 respectively) [7] In our study about 12 (34.2%) patients were managed medically while 23(65.5%) patients were managed by surgical method.

Conclusion

Uterine fibroid is the most common benign tumor of smooth muscle of uterus accounting for approximately 60% of total cases. Most common type being intramural and most common presenting symptoms is menorrhagia. Submucosal type affects

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